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PALACE OF THE KHWARAZMSHAHS

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The famous Toshhovli palace in Khiva, which still amazes the world, was built in 1829-1839 by order of Allaqulikhan (1794-1842) based on the project of the vizier Muhammad Yaqub Mehtar. This palace was built as the second Ark in Khiva, the palace of the ruler-khan. The name of the stone courtyard, built of fired bricks, is derived from the building's unique plan and architecture. In ancient times, buildings were short-lived because they were constructed from raw clay and timber. Later, bricks were fired in kilns, and stone buildings began to be built. Therefore, names appeared to distinguish them from one another, and the word "Tosh" was applied to many buildings. For example, there are many buildings and structures named after Toshkent, Toshhovuz, and the stone in Khiva: a stone mosque, a stone bridge, a stone gate, a stone well, a stone street, a stone lamp, a stone pit, etc. The stone courtyard palace consists of three large courtyards (view room, hotel, harem) and five small courtyards, a two-story porch, and rooms. First, the courtyards of the harem, then the hotel, and later the prayer hall were completed. While the khan's family lived in the harem, the hotel served distinguished guests such as foreign ambassadors, Turkmen leaders, and Karakalpak biys. If a citizen's complaint is heard in the courthouse, ambassadors from abroad are officially received here.

By order of Allahkulikhan, Muhammad Yusuf Mehtar rebuilt the Tashkhauz fortress in 1835, the mausoleums of Sultan Uvays Karani and Sheikh Muhammad Akhund Khorezmi in Kot-Kala in 1836–1838, and the mausoleums of Suleiman Bakirgani-Hakim-ota in Kungrad. In 1830, Allaqli Khan invited one physician from Shahrissabz and three physicians from India through Kamran, the Shah of Herat, to sponsor the development of medical science in the country.

This ruler died on the night of Tuesday, the 3rd day of the month of Zulq'ada, 1842. He lived for 49 years and reigned for 18 years. He left a name in history as a just, law-abiding, brave, and courageous khan. At his meetings, history and poetry were discussed, and anecdotes were told. He was survived by seven sons, two of whom—Rahimquli Tura and Muhammad Amin-inak—reigned as khans.

The most beautiful works of Khorezmian architects, miniaturists, tile masters, and wood and marble carvers are reflected in the Toshhovli Palace. One can only imagine how beautiful the palace is by looking at it. During the construction of the palace, the scholars of his time told many poetic stories about this. Some of them are engraved on the tiles inside the palace.

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The Arzkhana, which was called the viewing room or reception room in the Toshhovli, was also a courtyard with a high veranda, like in the Old Ark, and a high round platform was built in front of its veranda. A yurt was installed on this platform, where the guests were given a feast.

Abdulla Boltayev (1890-1966), who saw and heard the Khan's reception in the Arzkhana with his own eyes, wrote this. During the reception ceremony, the khan is surrounded by the yasovulbashi, the mehtar, the kushbegi, the shotirs (the riders of the khan's horse, who are four people on both sides of the khan's horse, dressed in red clothes, with bells hanging from their belts), and other servants. Carpets, rugs, and good felt mats are laid out on the veranda, and tiger skins are thrown over them. Every day, two and a half hours before sunset, the Khan would leave the harem and sit on a throne near the pillar of the prayer hall porch to listen to the complaint. One of the guards comes out to the gate and calls the petitioners in turn to the reception. A person who has come with a complaint begins by saying, "Sir, I have a complaint." After the Khan looked at him and said, "Say your request," he began to say his request. "Those who come to file a complaint enter through one door and leave through another."

After the reception in the palace, the Khan retires to his room. After that, all close officials enter to greet the Khan and make their appearance. They would go home only after the Khan had retired to his harem, that is, after he had gone inside.

Furthermore, the fact that the hotel was built for the khan's honored guests can be inferred from the fact that even ambassadors from abroad were accommodated in the house of a rich man or an official. He was invited to the palace only after the Khan announced when he would receive him. The fact that such respected guests as the Turkmen leaders in the khanate or the Kazakh and Karakalpak biys had their own friends in the capital did not necessitate a hotel for them. If the Khan wished, he would invite them into the drawing room. The architectural description of this courtyard can be found in the inscriptions on the tiles of the hotel veranda wall.

In the center of the hotel porch, on the wooden door of the room that enters from the southern wall, the following prayer is written in Arabic, in nasta'liq script:

May fortune and victories always accompany this magnificent castle.

The hotel consists of a courtyard surrounded by two-story rooms, with the most beautiful rooms located on the first and second floors in the center of the high porch on the south side of the courtyard. The room on the first floor is covered from bottom to top with beautifully carved blue tiles, and the ceiling is decorated

with golden and red Khiva patterns. The room on the second floor is enriched with examples of extremely delicate ganch carving, wood and copper carving. In the middle of the courtyard, there were two platforms designed for setting up.

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